

LITERATURE REVIEW OF RECENT NAVIGATION AND STABILITY OF SHIP

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ABSTRACT

This appraisal presents the current situation in the marine/stability/navigation industry and current beliefs of most the people in the field excluding this author plus at most a hand full of other individuals. While the previous literature review of the field by this author was largely done focusing on the transition from the belief in pivot in the metacenter to the belief in the pivot point at the mass centroid. While both pivot points are wrong yet both dominate the field usage as this review demonstrates.

Previously this author reviewed the initial history (17xx-197x), this paper is focus on the last year or so and what most of researchers' current point of view. This paper is not discussing what is at the forefront of the field as it will require almost exclusive review of this author's work. This paper is focusing on the errors currently dominate the industry and speculated why the belief in these errors are so persisting.

Advanced topics, such as continuous or discrete moving pivot points during the period will be presented in another paper. These advances will be published but with the reactions presented in this field hints that it will take a long time the material to be adapted as there are many people like minion from Norwegian University of Science and Technology and his masters. The change of the added moment due to the orientation is discussed as this topic was published by this author and others. Since no one presented and it is very logical (it is not really controversial), it should be accepted for the fair minded researchers.

NOMENCLATURE

Points of Interest

- A** Pivot point at the liquid level
- B** Buoyancy centroid
- G** Mass centroid

GM Distance between **M** and **G**

M Metacenter none existent and imaginary point

Z A point on **GM** perpendicular to **B'**

Variables

R_{EA_1} Arbitrary value 4.64 [m/s^2] the limit value

k_L A factor which accounting for coupling of roll with other ship motions;

g Gravity constant

h Height above the roll axis of the location considered

Greek Letters

ω The ship roll period

θ Characteristic roll amplitude

Key Words

Ship Navigation, Why wrong ideas are so entrenched, Added Moment of Inertia, Pivot Point locations, Transfer Properties

1 Introduction

The ship and/or the floating body is governed by equation(s) intensely depends on the moment of inertia, which in turn depends on the pivot point. Commonly, it has been believed that the floating body is like a regular pendulum, but larger that rotates around the metacenter and later (around 195x), around mass centroid (Bar-Meir 2023e). The aim of this article is to take samples of typical ideas and errors that dogged the field and check if it is possible to bring people back to science. What and how to eradicate these faulty ideas from the field. This discussion must present the real knowledge versus the believed and politically correct accepted "knowledge". It is hoped that these "scientists" will be willing to present their idea and challenge this author in disputation for all to see and judge.

This field of ship stability/navigation is one of the oldest and can trace its roots to Archimedes and others from that era. This field attracted the lucidest individuals, just to name a few, L. Euler, D. Bernoulli, Pierre Bouguer, William Froude and etc. This field has fostered many advances in mathematics like perturbation methods, numerical methods (Bouguer's trapezoid integration methods), etc. Yet, this field is deceiving to the point that as even phenomena that should appear in plain sight yet seems to be invisible like the transfer properties. The main reason that these phenomena are not visible because the right questions are not asked. The first question that should be posed on the rotation, where is the location of pivot point and what is the added moment of inertia. The history and reverence to Bouguer was so high that no one has challenged these questions as it will be discussed because the assumptions were regarded as holy ideas. Bouguer who became a professor at age 15 and who beat Euler in a math competition cannot be wrong. Yet, the idea that the angle rotation can be somehow calculated without knowing where is pivot point, is more than strange. Yet, it is the direct results of influence of Bouguer and his followers.

As these concepts were not enough, the added mass (and added moment of inertia) appended additional hurdles. Physics does not have a preferred coordinate system. While in theory, it seems that everyone agrees with this statement, yet in practice the situation is the opposite. For example, Fossen (2011) has advocated, (and many others) have adapted idea that the added mass coefficients or components are independent of each other. Following Fossen's and other logic have suggested or provided hints of the following two conflicting scenarios which cannot be co-exist or in other words both scenarios cannot be true in the same time. Suppose that Fossen's advocated idea is correct, the acceleration in one direction changes (either increases or decreases because an external force or other reasons) while in the other directions, the acceleration remains constant. According the Fossen and others, the total added mass remains the same (constant). This conclusion is immediately observed from the governing suggested by Fossen and others. Yet, in the same time, the added mass must be based on the direction of the force (for example, for the narrow direction, the added mass is small). Thus, on one hand according to people like Fossen it has to be constant yet the physics tell us that it requires to be based on the direction. Clearly this conflicting ideas cannot coexist. This conflict means that Fossen's advocated idea is actually pure rubbish.

The next point that essentially seems invisible or transparent is the transfer properties. These properties are not well known in the industry or basically are ignored in the industry. While some individuals have noticed that these properties are missing like Brennen (1982) but he and others conflated the transfer properties with the added mass. The added mass (moment of inertia) requires an acceleration while the transfer properties require velocity or change of location. For example, the heave (movement up or down) movement change liquid potential which re-

quires force (this movement partially was noticed by von Karman (1929).) This author noticed these properties due to the roll motion. The transfer property actually demonstrates that the GM is actually not useful in the rolling motion but AG . This fact is opposite to faulty idea that plagues the industry.

An additional point, the strip theory is valid as long as it is done properly which is not the case for all the research works done as writing this paper. The basic idea of the strip theory is that body can be broken to small slices which can be added to calculated the whole body. However, the application of this approach requires to account the effect the neighboring strips which was ignored in today's work (Bar-Meir 2023a). Additionally, the pivot point is determined for two phase scenario at liquid surface due to the gravity (2023c) and the none gravity case is calculated using (2023b).

One of the prevailing and defective idea is the Maneuvering Modeling Group (MMG) model, a committee decided model that is basically four degrees of freedom (ignoring two directions) (2015). Since it was made by a committee they did not feel that real science has to be inserted into the model. This fact manifested in not using proper none dimensionalize technique only the poor man technique (see section 2 of the said paper using π theory). The model is based five assumptions on which only the first three are reasonable. The fourth assumption actually requires dimensional analysis. The assumption should not be made. The assumption demonstrates lake of the idea or knowledge where is the pivot point and thus actually it is wrong. "Metacentric height GM is sufficiently large, and the roll coupling effect on maneuvering is negligible." Unfortunately, the GM is not directly connected (influence) the floating body stability or righting moment so this assumption is really meaningless. Preliminary dimensional analysis this author has done shows that the roll has stronger effect while the yaw has significantly less effect on the ship movement. This author analysis is not fully conclusive and refinement for certain ranges is still needed. Nevertheless, it questions the validity MMG model. Furthermore, the equations in MMG build with the assumption that the added properties are constant which is very crude with other errors such wrong pivot point. In addition missing the main mechanisms of the energy loss, the model creates hundreds percents error.

The building base for Xu et al's model (2024) attempted to check the validity (called sensitivity) of 3 degree of freedom versus the full six but the comparison is faulty. The common idea of MMG with 3 degree of freedom (sway, surge, yaw) as compared to the full 6 degree of freedom is not based on science. While the dimensional analysis by current author demonstrates that most of the energy loss is due to roll and heave as oppose to Xu et al's assumption. "[T]hat dynamics associated with the motion in heave, roll, and pitch are neglected," the heave and roll are the most taxing of the energy (loss). Furthermore, the authors did not define the angle of yaw, or roll or/and pitch thus this minion make the whole analysis meaningless. This analysis

is similar to person losing his key in the middle of the street and yet he is looking for key at edge of the street because there is street light.

2 Strip Theory

Abdelwahab et al (2023) suggested a model to study wave-induced ship motions. According to this research group “typically the wave-induced loads account for about 60% of the loads while the other 40% are due to the still-water loads”. The calculations are based on the erroneous strip theory. No wonder the authors got such strange results. Not using the right equations and expect to get realistic results should not be envisioned. Beside the faulty strip theory usage, the main lost is due to the change in the added mass in reality. The report abstract many important details of the model (who let this paper to be published?) but it can be assumed (from the way the situation is described) that pivot point is at the mass centroid. The analysis also used the wave Green’s function which also based on neglecting variation of the added properties and hence it is erroneous as well. The change of the added mass (all the properties) is assumed to be zero while the hydrodynamic forces by steering depending on the angle. This schizophrenic idea should be rejected unless serious considerations are done especially at first glance suggest the opposite and when literature review shows that it was never properly done.

3 In The General View

Example of general fallacies is given by Seo et al (2024). The authors considered what is optimal ship hull without image what are the parameters what affect the hull. The authors claimed that “[t]he shape of a ship’s hull, the outermost surface of a vessel that comes into contact with water, is one of the most crucial design factors in terms of the fuel economy of a vessel. A ship’s operating conditions at the free surface give rise to different kinds of resistance components: viscous resistance and wave-making resistance. The latter part is closely related to the bow hull form.” One of the main energy loss is due to the added mass change which was neglected.

4 The Heave Oscillations Special Cases

Jing et al (2023) studied the heave movement for two bodies side by side that have change of elevation due to wave propagating from the side. The focus was on the liquid level in the gap between the two bodies. The case is examined here because it presents a special case outside the regular configuration of floating body but has the similar Mechanisms. As expected, Jing et al failed to include the added mass. The paper quoting others and states that “[h]owever, the key parameters of the damping term always rely on experimental data, and indeed, it has been

demonstrated that there is no a priori method of determining the coefficient of the damping term unless it is calibrated by experimental tests (Pauw et al., 2007; Feng et al., 2017).” The reason that these “coefficients” can not be “found” is because the authors ignored the added mass change, something that von Karman (1929) demonstrated a hundred year ago on similar problem (no literature review, really?). The combination of the sway and heave changes the added mass (for the heave) and hence changes the frequency of gap liquid. This situation is similar to swimming to the pool edge where the added mass increases (Bar-Meir 2023c). Yet this work did not account for this important effect. Statements like “[b]ased on the above gradually matured methods” is only indication of the poor quality of this work.

Chen et al suggested that “[a]s a ship is sailing in stern quartering seas, the encounter frequency may be low due to the Doppler effect” (2023). No physical explanation was provided and does not seem to be based any physical reasoning and no real experimental evidence is provided. It could be that authors refer to the visible frequency observed by the ship coordinates system. Thus, this claim does not seem, at this stage, worth any examination. However, one of the strange approaches typical of marine engineering is based on how many degree of freedoms are employed. Chen et al review (on the second page second paragraph) provides array of such combinations even with asking or questioning why the combination determines the rolling movement. Yet, Chen et al choose to use six degrees of freedoms for a body that has continuous pivot points. This paper assumes no added mass is needed. See for the explanation why the added mass is needed (Bar-Meir 2023d). Clearly if the major elements are neglected such added mass, pivot points etc one should not expect results related to reality.

Jiao et al (2023) published an editorial article which demonstrates several flaws in the understating of the authors, as they presented “a collection of 11 high-quality research”. It is not clear how they determined what is “high-quality” research. Maybe one of this collection was written by the Jiao et al and others maybe related to them. While all the research they presented are simply flawed in a very extreme way, one wonder what makes it “high-quality”. All the papers presented have similar errors and serious flaws in the models with some of them assuming no added mass (moment of inertia). For example, they mentioned Ravenna et al. as calculating due to the viscosity while ignoring the energy loss due to resistance due to the change of the added mass when the boundary’s effect on added mass totally ignored. Furthermore, Ravenna et al was using a poor man dimensional analysis instead of the real one. How this approach can be considered high quality? Not to mention that one of the article they review is one of the authors article (ref 6) which seem to be not ethical.

5 No Added Mass

Yu et al (2023) study the “the seakeeping performance of the surge-free ship models accurately and efficiently.” Yu et al assumed that no added mass and without identifying angles of rotation because the pivot point does not mentioned in the paper. The authors mentioned a strange non-linear effect without specifying what and why they do not act the same way as the “other” effects. It is interesting the Yu et al’s model is based on Fourier series but, yet no explanation is provided to why.

Beig and Schmidt (2021) studied the stability of floating bodies from the mathematical point of view. It is amazing that real literature review was not required for that work. As the question, the mathematicians are interest to solve is the “famous question of Ulam [6] regarding whether there are bodies other than spheres which have equilibria in every orientation”. It is interesting that the researchers are trying to reinvent the dimensional analysis and yet ignore important concepts such as pivot point. How one can check the “famous” when one does not use the pivot point? Is the pivot point is irrelevant? The answer they post is there no such body if the body has uniform density. The proof is very simple and it is based on the improved Paul Erdős (1992) idea that stability must have minimum distance between the pivot point to the gravity. The only configuration that has this situation this condition exist is a cylinder in two dimensional domain and a sphere in three dimensional domain. There is no need need to spend time on this question.

Pan et al (2023) studied the wave and how to find representation of the wave phenomenon. Pan et al suggested a mathematical representation which still needs a physical explanation. Yu et al (2023) studied the oblique wave effects (force and moment/torque) on the ship. The first assumption of linearity is very questionable as the effects that make the oblique shock in compressible flow does not exist here (see for more information (2021a)). Thus, for example slamming the ship on starboard side (right side) or port side (left side) creates moment in the three directions. In the model used by Yu et al the added mass was assumed to be constant and zero. Clearly neglecting the added mass make the whole model worthless. It is interesting that the zero added mass as well as moment of inertia belief still live and kicking these days. The model promotes the idea that wave is perfect hyperbolic phenomena is unrealistic and there is strong elliptical elements. It is like still finding a flat earth believers, nothing can convince them. Hyperbolic phenomena is situation where downstream conditions do not affect upstream conditions while in elliptical phenomena is the opposite, hand waving speaking.

Dong et al (2023) studied the wave effects on the ship movement. According to Dong et al the ship respond differently to low frequency than to high frequency. “When sailing in waves, ships are significantly affected by the low-frequency wave drift forces, known as the second-order wave forces.” Generally, it is expected that the frequency should strong effects on the float-

ing body movements. This author expect that in very low and very high frequencies to be minimal effects. The stronger effect will be somewhere in the middle in one or several discreet zones. It should be expect that these certain ranges should be pointed which this research work failed to mentioned. Especially because in this work no dimensional analysis was done. This aspect is basically too opaque to be considered serious as something that has to be taken care. This paper was utilizing the faulty MMG thus it is assumed that the work full of errors.

6 GM Effects

The change of ship or floating body’s **GM** was investigated by Song et al (2024). The change of **GM** is related to heave movement and the change of the loading. Where the first is temporary while the second is permanent. Song et al refer here only to the change of the load and assume that the **GM** is directly affecting the stability and the rolling frequency. Of course this **GM** effect is wrong and as usual no explanation or logic is provide to this “fact”. Again the added mass was assume to zero and unchanged. Furthermore, without proper dimensional analysis three degree of freedom were arbitrary were selected (surge, sway, and yaw). These directions are not reasonable according preliminary analysis done by this author. Paroka (2023) summarized the common that appeared in IMO (International Maritime Organization) known as the Second Generation Intact Stability Criteria (SGISC). Basically a document that summarizes the lake of knowledge or the dominate prevailing superstitions in the field. Boccadamo (2019) study the effects of the acceleration on stability and looking at the **GM**. This criteria for the acceleration is basically build up of not relating items and made a nice salad. For example, the acceleration equation is

$$\theta k_L \left(g + 4 \pi^2 \frac{h}{\omega^2} \right) < R_{EA1} \quad (1)$$

where:

R_{EA1}	arbitrary value 4.64 [m/s^2] the limit value
θ	characteristic roll amplitude
k_L	a factor which accounting for coupling of roll with other ship motions;
g	gravity acceleration
h	height above the roll axis of the location considered
ω	the ship roll period.

The majority of the elements of the equation are meaningless as the term “characteristic roll amplitude” has no real meaning. The experimental k_L is basically a joke since it provides no physics base or logic while h is not really defined. This equation is not based on physical reasoning and should be reconstructed. The second equation in the paper is full of fallacies that are beyond

reasonable discussion. For example, it employs two rotations one around metacenter and one around mass centroid (these two rotation cannot coexist). Note that these authors assume that exciting moment should be expand to a Taylor series (no explanation why).

7 Design Roll Stabilization Controller

Lee et al (2011) designed a study on how to design roll stabilization controller assuming that the ship is rotated around the mass centroid. This pivot violates the second law of the thermodynamics as it was shown in (Bar-Meir 2023e). Simply stating, this model is not reasonable. Additionally, the authors assumed without dimensional analysis or logical explanation why only sway roll yaw motions are used (see for motions definition in (Bar-Meir 2021b)). In this case, it can be observed that motion in these directions are decoupled and do not effecting each other. Also the pivot point of yaw depends on rudder and other parameters which were not included. As all the works in this area, no dimensional analysis was really done on the bilge keel (in that article it is referred to as fin (not exactly bilge). Chen et al (2021) use the explanation to Taylor series describe the waves effects (versus Fourier series). As it was discussed in Bar-Meir (Bar-Meir 2023e) no one seems to be able provide any substantive physical explanation. Of course with the typical errors, such as the added mass issue etc one should not expect any real results from this work. Chen et al (2023) studied what they referred to as extreme roll (small ship dimension). In this situation there is a phenomenon that requires a dimensional analysis and yet the researchers utilize hand waving analysis. “This situation may lead to the wave crest passing the midship section of a ship with a speed higher than the ship’s forward speed, causing the relatively small restoring arm and this state exists long enough.” This situation referred by the authors as the Doppler effect. While it directly related to heave and roll many researchers (such as (Lilienthal, Matsuda, and Thomas 2007)) attached to surge-roll (side movement to a rotation of the small dimension).

Cakici et al (2024) have reported on the fin a similar device to bilge keel but much shorter and that could has a rotation ability. Cakici et al have done a short literature survey of the typical errors carried (they did not realize that these points are actually erroneous). These errors include ignoring the added mass (later it was included), the change of the added mass value which causes large resistance or energy lost (due to the change of angle). As a typical of work in this field no dimensional analysis was conducted thus the discussion on one degree of freedom versus four degree of freedom is actually meritless. The claim that four degree of freedom is more accurate than the one degree of freedom is wrong when additional errors are introduced. Additionally, the authors assumed that pivot point is around mass centroid which introduces other errors into the calculations.

The strip theory has been around for about 50 years and

more and went through total overrule as there was a more flaws in the derivation (Bar-Meir 2023a). Not so recent work McTaggart (2011) discuss the “success” of the strip theory. “Strip theory (Salvesen, Tuck and Faltinsen, 1970) has been used for many years by the Canadian Navy, and provides surprisingly good motion predictions for slender naval vessels.” The fact that implication of the strip theory in these works has flaws apparently is irrelevant (sorry for the tone)¹. Additionally, a question of dimensional analysis of at what range the velocity the strip theory can be used but hand wave was use instead. Another idea Hull hydrodynamic forces are computed in the frequency domain using the zero—speed Green function that do have serious faults. The reasons that this idea is nonsense because solving, the wrong equations and the added mass not properly considered do not provide good results. A recommend zero—spread Green function technique suggested by others is not appropriate as it not solving the right equations. “Hull hydrodynamic forces are computed in the frequency domain using the zero-speed Green function, similar to the approach used by Papanikolaou and Schellin (1992).” It is interesting that this technique not commonly used these days.

Matsui et al (2023) studied the response of the roll to wavy sea. It is not clear why the word “wavy sea” has a special meaning or effect in this context. Matsui alleged that “[t]oday, sea-keeping tools such as the strip method (Salvesen et al., 1970) and the Green’s function method (Papanikolaou and Schellin, 1992) can estimate hull motions with a certain degree of rationality, but this requires information on the hull form and its data preparation.” While these claims are questionable at best, it demonstrates, at least, that some “genius” believe in these “scientific” techniques even though governing equation are wrong. The slender body assumption can be used the strip technique **only and only** when it properly implemented. Matsui et al assumed three degree of freedoms The Green function requires some kind of linearity which not exist (or it at least very weak) in this case. The selection of the roll, sway, and yaw elements without any serious dimensional analysis seems capricious. As the authors confused between the added mass elements to the actual added mass and constructed the governing equation assuming (seems) rotation at the mass centroid.

He et al (2023) examined the energy losses components. In that review, they considered traditional components such as better fuel and better engine (not a marine concerned but general mechanical engineering), improving the propulsion system (for example rudder), like the first and a variant “alternative”energy (like sails wind turbine). Another item on the green agenda is the resistance reduction. This item includes the smoothing the surface (coating), hulls configuration (for resistance), innovative ideas (such as bubble injection to reduce skin friction resistance). He pointed to “[a]nother energy-saving operation includes route

¹It is strange to talk about my other academic grandfather, Tuck who pass not long ago.

and speed optimization.” None of these ideas does contain the major energy loss which is the energy loss due to change of the added mass especially with wavy sea. Why one does not include the major elements if not the major in analyzing the energy loss?

Luo et al (2023) studied the ship roll motion and they believe that natural frequency based on the waves (there is no explanation or logic for this belief). Is this paper another paper where the authors are clueless on the physics? or is the physics irrelevant? Is the pivot point has to be guessable? And here it is assumed to be at the mass centroid, maybe? Beside the violating thermo second law pivot point, this work also assumes that righting arm is somehow related to the **GM**. Now with so many errors especially when these errors have been shown in the literature, one can wonder why someone write so much nonsense?

8 The Famous Minion

This author got several letters from a Ph.D. student in the Norwegian University of Science and Technology group who would like to be called **THE Norwegian Scientist** with Roger Skjetne as his advisor. This author considers this individual as Thor Fossen and Roger Skjetne’s minion. The graduate student wrote to this author to express this sentiment about none existent of pivot point in ship navigation. This issue is brought into this paper because it represents many misunderstandings which must to be illuminated and eliminated. One particular issue has be brought in this paper and more of these letters will be follow up the next articles. The red indicating the extracts from the minion’s letters sent to this author.

Your criticism appears to hinge on the existence (or rather non-existence) of a pivot point (also known as roll center). Observe that the model presented in Marley et al (2023) includes roll-sway coupling, and hence the pivot point is not a part of the discussion. The choice of origin, or vertical reference point, makes no difference on the roll motion, but it does of course influence the roll-sway coupling terms and the sway motion.

As oppose to minion’s physics, the real physics requires that a solid body moves with a velocity of pivot point and rotation for a plain single pivot rotation point. The insinuating alleged multi pivot points scenario by the minion is not possible in the real physics. This schizophrenic statement is totally wrong as both moment of inertia of the ship and the added moment of inertia depend on the pivot point. This point is stated in this author papers (is the minion lack the ability of reading comprehension genuine? Or is he just a facade pretend stupidity? It is hard to believe that one can be so dumb.). Again every rotation movement of solid body must have a actual pivot point. It is not the reference or origin of coordinate system but the pivot point. It is not clear why this point is controversial (maybe the minion did not play with toy in his childhood?). It should be recognized that when body rotates, **it must** have a single pivot point

for a plane (2D). The literature review done by this author did not reveal any reference that roll causes sway (this claim is new i. e. never had any proof or logical explanation) or simply cyclic, may be THE Norwegian Scientist has somewhere hidden reference or real logical explanation dealing with this connection.). It must be pointed out, the idea advocated by Alexandra Techet from MIT in her class material that one generic movement affects another movement is an urban legend and it is discussed in (Bar-Meir 2022) and will be focused in one of the next installment in the series of “Simplified Ship Rolling Calculations”. Fundamentally the source of this urban legend is the added mass matrix itself influenced. This idea conflates the way of the construction of added mass coefficients to the physical affects. To put it in another way, simply stating like the regular mass, the added mass itself does not create coupling but the change in shape, orientation, and etc creates the coupling.

Four degree of freedom require at least one pivot point. The special combination that the minion’s (not clear if he was told to write so) selection is one of the special case when sway (at a constant velocity) does not effect the roll yet, the roll affects the sway due to change of the added mass. As demonstration consider sitting on a ship with a constant sway velocity, the roll movement will have the same governing equation as zero sway velocity. This claim is a perfect example why all most the works that produced by these field elders violate the second law of thermodynamics and there are doubts if any other parts of their work can be salvaged. In this case, the view that the roll is created by sway movement because the minion or his masters want it, is not based on the physics laws. The term that the Norwegian Scientist use “roll center” is used mostly for cars and has different meaning to what the minion claims. In nautical or marine purposes it is seldom used to indicate not the pivot point but rather a point that is temporary used by roll movement (Fernandes, Asgari, and Soares 2016). In fact, it accentuates the fact of lack of understanding of the “scientists” as they claim that “a very rough estimate for the location of the roll center is halfway between the center of gravity and the center of buoyancy.” Furthermore, according to them, this center is only temporary that it is sometime work and sometime does not.

All this talk about pivot point tells me you have a very limited understanding or knowledge of ship dynamics. It appears you are knocking on open doors. The topics you raise are either well-known in todays ship dynamics community, or blatantly wrong.

What is your definition of pivot point? One definition is the vertical elevation at which the sway velocity is zero when excited by harmonic waves. Obviously this point will depend on the wave period.

The “crystal clear” statement about zero sway rotation to mean rolling rotation around a different plane, how the minion’s rota-

tion is possible. As before, the minion and his masters allegations are always vague (what claims are known and what claims are wrong are not provided or specified). They are fussy on the reference showing where and who learn about these advances and how they similar. One can wonder why field elders always pull out the claim of “we always knew that” when it is very easy to prove the opposite. It will be interesting to find any reference, as alleged by minion or his master, to the ideas of this author in the literature.

The pivot point is a point were a solid body (ship for example) is rotating around. The definition that used in the minion’s statement is not clear. If the claim is understood correctly there is no such point. If there is a different meaning from the written statement then there is no known appriori way to calculate the location because it is not based on physical principles. Furthermore, it is not the actual point the ship pivot. The Norwegian Scientist stated “What is your definition of pivot point?” Over dozens pages in several papers (actually four papers) have been written just about this point. It is recommended to the minion or his masters and people like them to read these papers. Thus, the record is a strong indication that the minion just did not read the articles. Additionally, in the case of zero sway, according to the minion multiply pivot points exist (it will be nice to find solid bodies with multiply pivot points or zero on the same plane of the body.

Belenky et al (2024) studied the capsizes of ships. “The paper summarizes almost three decades of research on the probability of ship capsizing in irregular waves.” According to this statement in the abstract is indication how facts and proofs do not sway “scientists” in what is going in the field. Again, equation (2) (their model) of that paper, the authors assumed **GM** is righting arm and the added mass is constant. As customary in the field the rotation of angle is not defined. But from the examination of the paper is seems that is around the mass centroid and hence the model violates the second law of thermodynamics. The strange and bizarre definition never cease to amaze. “where I_x is the transverse moment of inertia of the “dry” hull”. What is the meaning of “dry” hull? Is different pivot point? The fact that none of these terms is really is more than indication of authors for lack of understanding. Another meaningless paper by similar authors (Glotzer, Pipiras, Belenky, Weems, and Sapsis 2024) was dealing with similar equations and further push it to the fairy realm. In the same vein (2024) another example that exceed the absurd, the authors did even bother to state their governing equations. In the said paper the authors studied the critical wave groups method that might be interesting but implement the erroneous model of the ship.

9 Concluding Remarks

This paper provides a review of the strange situation in ship stability and navigation where the vast majority is using the erro-

neous models that violate the second law of thermodynamics. The field full of papers that when one ask very basic and fundamental questions while the author cannot answer them. For example, how the angle is defined and where and why the rotation point is determined. Clearly, these kind of questions plus lack of proper dimensional analysis set the field back and make it more of black art.

Here, in this paper is not describing several other breakthroughs which explain the jerking of the ship during the rotation. Here, the focus is on the obvious the entranced falsities of the field and the reasons for their existence. It is strange to model without added mass, or pivot point at the metacenter while the same group can publish a paper with pivots point the mass centroid. While the ridiculous beliefs in marine creatures locomotion were not discussed here but might be addressed in next paper in this line. It lovely to see several minions that attacked this author especially Fossen’s minion as they provide incentive of science promotion.

Currently this author is overloaded with questions and unfinished material and parts are in a draft form and may or may not be published and might join the faith of many unpublished papers of this author, laying in his boxes. A small point, in writing these papers a new technology was used. The equations derivations were typed straight into enclosed confidential and supper confidential environments (for this author eyes only) which should not appear in the final version. Hence, if something is rasping, this writing style is one of causes of the “small black dots”.

Disputation

After the minions one from Norwegian University of Science and Technology and his masters issuing the claims that either all was known or if it was not known it must be wrong, here is a challenge for him and his masters (the minions are not discussed). Additionally there are those quietly believe these claims without advertise their beliefs. Furthermore, there are those who put on the horse blindfold to minimize their exposure the new technology like Carolyn Q. Judge so they will not realize their work were useless/wrong. With about five billion dollars in research grants and producing research papers that violate the second law of thermodynamics it is time to examine these erroneous claims. This author is calling for disputation since the subject is science. If you believe in one or more of the topics below you have invitation for disputation.

These topics are

1. The pivot point of the rolling or pitching is either in the metacenter or mass centroid or “rolling center”. The rolling center mentioned in this paper. Or pivot point is somewhere strange like 1/3 distance between x to y .
2. The moment of inertia is independent of the pivot point.
3. Added mass or the added moment of inertia is constant.

4. The pivot point is constant in the ship navigation equations.
5. If you believe that MMG equations are correct.
6. If you believe the traditional strip theory as it describe in MIT's class.
7. If you believe that added mass is not actually a single added mass.
8. If you believe that more 20% of the world research in the ship stability navigation does not violate the second law of thermodynamics.

Acknowledgment

This paper describe progress in this magnitude has some willing and unwilling partners (some of the exposed and some not). First, thank you for Kate Budziak who correct the English of early draft of the first 5 pages which her questions added more material. Second, the unwilling participants such as Carolyn Q. Judge from USNA that set to “protect” her students from the truth and the minion. Several other individuals from Gdańsk University that through the discussions with them demonstrate how the fads persuasive around the world. Some discussion elements on parallel theorem remained and persist in this paper please ignore those. Also Spyrou by his plagiarizing demonstrated how the establishment deal with the “rogue agent” by netscaping their material.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author's models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Bar–Meir was instrumental in developments of the added mass (properties) concepts. He differentiate between the added

properties and the transfer properties. He discovered the change of the added mass (the general form) and its effects on the governing equations. He invented the stability dome for floating bodies and in the process developed the equation for location of centroid of circle segment.

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar–Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared in the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar–Meir's book. Dr. Spyrou's behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar–Meir's calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford University recently decided to copy Bar–Meir's idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to it in his book (and probably also in his classes). Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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